

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' KINESTHETIC DEVELOPMENT DURING THEIR PREPARATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *This article examines the importance of developing students' professional skills, motivation, professional development, and the use of innovative educational technologies in the modern education system. It analyzes the influence of psychological and pedagogical factors on the process of improving educational and methodological support in line with international requirements and the development of future specialists as well-rounded individuals. Special emphasis is placed on the role of motives, needs, internal incentives, and interests in professional development, as well as the readiness of young people to choose a profession.*

Keywords: *professional skills, motivation, innovative education, holistic personality development, educational technologies, psychological-pedagogical factors, career choice.*

Introduction

Education is recognized as a key factor in the modern international development system, ensuring sustainable development in our century. At the international education forum in the Republic of Korea, the importance of "creating opportunities for quality education throughout life" was emphasized within the framework of the Vision 2030 framework. This, in turn, has expanded the opportunities for developing educational and methodological support for the professional training of future teachers using educational technologies aimed at developing students' professional skills, organizing their professional and practical training based on an innovative approach, and fostering independent thinking, creativity, and ingenuity.

With the informatization of the global education system, research is underway to update educational and methodological support for developing the professional skills of future professionals in line with international requirements, as well as to clarify the psychological and pedagogical factors in developing students' professional skills. In addressing these challenges, the development of methodological resources for the development of professional skills and their improvement based on an innovative approach, the creation of the necessary pedagogical conditions, and the use of modern educational technologies to improve the quality and effectiveness of education are relevant.

Main part

One of the key areas of educational reforms implemented in our country is the development of each representative of the younger generation as a comprehensively developed, educated, and, undoubtedly, harmonious individual. Naturally, a harmonious individual is understood as the upbringing of a spiritually mature individual who cares about the history, present, and future of their homeland and is eager to contribute to the development of society, which resonates with the demands of today. An analytical approach to this concept reveals how multifaceted and complex it is, and how comprehensively it aligns with universal human values. It can be said that this implies the development of a harmonious individual, their mastery of a worthy profession, their

worthy contribution to the development of society, and, through this, self-awareness and self-realization in society—in short, the development of a comprehensively mature individual.

The pursuit of excellence is a complex, holistic process that occurs simultaneously with professional development and continues practically throughout life. More precisely, professional development is understood as a person receiving an education in a certain professional field in accordance with his mental abilities, physical capabilities, predisposition to a particular field, interests and aspirations, as well as values and worldview, with subsequent entry and adaptation in this field and, finally, becoming a mature and qualified specialist over many years.[1, p. 53]

The initial and most important stage of professional development encompasses the period of choosing a future profession, that is, the time before making a specific professional decision. It is well known that in the continuing education system for ninth-grade students and graduates of general secondary education, the eve of graduation is a time filled with youthful feelings and passions, when they strive to realize their future dreams and hopes. In ontogenesis, this period is characterized by such features as the acquisition of civil status by young people entering independent life, as well as the formation of their personal, social, and spiritual views and beliefs. Therefore, it is precisely during this time that the responsibility of authorized persons should increase to help young people set the right goals at the threshold of life and subsequently move forward confidently and boldly.

As is well known, motives are a source of inner strength, impelling a person to act to achieve a specific goal. Motives manifest themselves in the process of human activity as specific needs and are satisfied through its implementation. Motives for human activity have various forms and structures, for example: organic, functional, material, social, spiritual, and so on. It is also necessary to enhance an individual's academic motivation by fostering a positive attitude toward their chosen profession. It is well known that one of the socially conditioned human qualities is personal direction, or motivation. Motivation is an important psychological process within the personality structure, directing all actions toward a common and unified goal, stimulating and fully ensuring its stable functioning. Motives, needs and interests, inclinations and desires, and internal stimuli constitute the core of motivation. [3, p. 12]

A person's abilities or professional skills are formed and developed depending on their "environment" (the environment can also hinder their development). "Environment" refers to the family, preschool, school, lyceum, college, higher education institution, work team, and microcommunity (friends, acquaintances, etc.). In other words, a skill originates in a person's "inner world" as a hereditary, biological ability or inclination based on interest. By its nature, it is a subjective quality that is formed and developed depending on objective conditions. Skill encompasses not only intellect but also affective behavior, abilities, and intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation determines an individual's values and, according to the scientist, is crucial in skill development. [2, p. 26]

Research results and discussion

Clearly, the concept of motivation, unlike the concept of motive, represents a broader psychological process aimed at achieving long-term goals and implementing long-term plans. Motivation, which develops within the personality structure in relation to professional skills, is a socially conditioned component and develops through education and upbringing. Based on the methods analyzed above, it should be noted that the primary goals of modern research should be: helping young people find their place in society, striving to earn the respect and recognition of others, proving their capabilities to themselves and others, further strengthening their faith in their

destiny and the future of their homeland, and, most importantly, further developing their professional skills. It is only natural that, in a context of dramatic change, reforms, and a shifting status of values, the attitudes of today's youth toward the future cannot leave anyone indifferent.

Conclusion

Thus, the essence, purpose, and content of education are determined by the level of cultural development of a society, its scientific and technological progress, the degree of implementation of industrial technologies, as well as the development of students' professional skills and their practical application. Depending on social relations, the demand and need for general education, the level of students' professional preparation, and their views on education, the essence, purpose, content, forms of organization, methods, and means of implementing education change and improve at different periods (stages) of society's development.

REFERENCES

1. Hamroeva M. *New Pedagogical Technologies and Teaching Excellence*. – T.: 2005
2. Kukushkin V.S. *Advanced pedagogical technologies*. – Rostov-on-Don, 2003
3. Bozorova S. *Technologies for Professionally Oriented Learning in Higher Education*. – T.:2006
4. Abdukudusov O. *An Integrative Approach to the Training of Vocational Teachers*. Tashkent: “FAN”, 2005.
5. Akhunov U.R. *A Method for Developing Motor Activity in Preschool-Age Children Through Physical Movement Theatre*. Monograph, Andijan, 2024.